

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of thorium(IV) with *N,N'*-propylenebis(3-carboxypropenamide) and various anions

M. Viswanathan

Department of Chemistry, S. N. College for Women, Kollam-691 001, India

E-mail : jaiviswam@yahoo.co.in jaiviswam@sancharnet.in

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A new series of mixed ligand complexes of thorium(IV) with *N,N'*-propylenebis(3-carboxypropenamide) [PBCPH₂] and various monovalent anions such as nitrate, perchlorate and thiocyanate have been synthesized. These complexes were characterised by chemical analysis, conductance, magnetic, X-ray powder diffraction, spectral and thermal studies. From these studies the composition of the complexes were ascertained to be [Th(PBCP)X₂] and [Th(PBCP)(ClO₄)OCIO₃], where X = NO₃⁻ or NCS⁻. In these complexes *N,N'*-propylenebis(3-carboxypropenamide) acts as a tetradentate ligand and monovalent anions act as unidentate ligands.

Studies of metal complexes of polydentate ligands containing amide groups have been reported in literature^{1,2}. In continuation of these studies, a polydentate ligand is prepared by treating maleic anhydride with propylenediamine. Further, some mixed ligand complexes of Th^{IV} with this ligand as primary ligand and various anions as secondary ligand were prepared and characterised by various physicochemical methods. The structure of the ligand may be represented as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were double-distilled before use.

The ligand PBCPH₂ was prepared by literature method. Maleic anhydride (0.1 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and to this propylenediamine (0.05 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring under ice cold conditions. The white solid formed was filtered, washed several times with acetone and dried. It was then purified by dissolving

in 5% solution of sodium carbonate and reprecipitated by addition of dilute hydrochloric acid in cold. The pure ligand has the melting point of 163°C and yield 85%.

Preparation of the complexes of thorium(IV) with PBCPH₂ :

The nitrate and perchlorate complexes were prepared by refluxing a methanolic solution of the ligand with the metal salt in stoichiometric amounts. For this, 0.001 mol of the respective metal salt was dissolved in methanol. To this, a solution of 0.001 mol of PBCPH₂ in methanol was added slowly and refluxed for 2-3 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to half of its volume and allowed to cool. The solid complexes formed were filtered, washed with methanol and acetone and finally dried over calcium chloride.

The thiocyanato complex was prepared by refluxing the nitrate complex with stoichiometric amounts of ammonium thiocyanate for 2-3 h.

The thorium content of the complex was determined by oxalate-oxide method³. The nitrate content of the complex was determined gravimetrically by using nitron reagent⁴. The thiocyanate content of the complex was determined gravimetrically as AgSCN⁴. The amount of perchlorate was determined by Kurz method⁵. For this, the perchlorate complex was heated in a muffle furnace with excess of sodium nitrite at about 500°C so that the perchlorate was reduced to chloride. The residue left was extracted with water and the chloride in the solution was estimated by Volhard's method. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were measured at room temperature by

Gouy method⁶. The infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} by KBr disc technique on a Perkin-Elmer 1650 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Molar masses of the complexes were determined by Rast method⁷ using biphenyl as the solvent. The conductance of the complexes were determined by Elico conductivity bridge type CM82T with a dip type conductivity cell by using 10^{-3} M solutions in methanol, acetonitrile, nitrobenzene and DMF.

The X-ray powder pattern of the complexes were recorded by using Philips diffractometer (Model PW 1710) for the nitrate and thiocyanato complexes of PBCPH₂ with thorium.

The TG and DTG curves of the complexes were recorded on a Mettler thermal analyzer model TA 3000 with a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{m}$ from ambient to 750°C . Independent pyrolysis experiment was also carried out for each of the complexes studied and loss of mass determined in each case was compared with that obtained from TG.

Results and discussion

The complexes are non hygroscopic crystalline solids. From the analytical data (Table 1) the complexes have the formula $[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})\text{ClO}_4]\text{OClO}_3$, where $\text{X} = \text{NO}_3^-$ or NCS^- .

Table 1. Analytical and molar mass data of the complexes of PBCPH₂ with the nitrate, thiocyanate and perchlorate of Th^{IV}

Complex	Thorium %	Anion %	Molar mass
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	36.48 (37.18)	19.22 (19.87)	636 (624)
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{NCS})_2]$	37.02 (37.66)	18.61 (18.83)	638 (616)
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{ClO}_4)]\text{OClO}_3$	32.84 (33.18)	28.20 (28.49)	712 (699.2)

Calculated values are given in parenthesis.

Molar conductivity values (Table 2) of the nitrate and thiocyanato complexes in acetonitrile, DMF, methanol and nitrobenzene were in the ranges corresponding to those of non electrolytes in all the solvents⁸ indicating that the anions were coordinated to the metal ions and hence act as additional ligands. The perchlorato complex

Table 2. Molar conductance data of the nitrate, thiocyanato and perchlorato complexes with PBCPH₂

Complex	Molar conductance, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$			
	Methanol	Acetonitrile	Nitrobenzene	DMF
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	28	5	3	20
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{NCS})_2]$	24	6	2	20
$[\text{Th}(\text{PBCP})(\text{ClO}_4)]\text{OClO}_3$	104	149	29	84

behaves like 1 : 1 electrolyte which indicates that one ClO_4^- is coordinated to the metal ion whereas the remaining ClO_4^- is outside the coordination sphere.

The magnetic data agree with the theoretical diamagnetic values expected for a $5f^0$ system.

The infrared spectrum of the ligand exhibits a stretching frequency of amide⁹ -NH at 3300cm^{-1} . A medium band at 3100cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ of carboxylic acid group which is hydrogen bonded with carbonyl group of the amide¹⁰. The band at 1700cm^{-1} is due to the stretching frequency of carbonyl group of carboxylic acid. The amide carbonyl stretching frequency¹¹ is observed at 1620cm^{-1} .

The proton NMR spectrum of PBCPH₂ recorded in DMSO shows a signal at 9.1 (2H, COOH). A quartet at 3.6 ppm (4H, CH₂) near to the secondary amide groups. A quintet at 2.05 ppm is given by the methylene protons in between the above mentioned methylene groups. A triplet at 8.2 ppm (2H, amide NH). A doublet of doublet at 6.1 ppm is due to -CH=CH-^{9,10}.

The mass spectrum of the ligand shows molecular ion peak at m/z 270 and a base peak at $m/z = 116$ due to $[\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4]^+$ ion. The peak at m/z 72 is due to $[\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-\text{COOH}]^+$ and one at m/z 45 is due to $[\text{COOH}]^+$.

The infrared spectra of the complexes show the tetradentate nature of the ligand with two carboxyl oxygen and two carbonyl groups of secondary amides acting as donor sites. The disappearance of the band at 3100cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ of the carboxyl group, shows the deprotonation of the acid group and its coordination through the hydroxyl oxygen. This is further supported by the disappearance of the characteristic carboxylic group absorption at 1700cm^{-1} and the appearance of two new bands at $1560\text{--}1540 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $1360\text{--}1340 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies respectively of coordinated carboxylate group. Shifting of the band at 1400cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of COOH group to a lower frequency of 1380cm^{-1} also supports the arguments of deprotonation of -COOH group and coordination through the hydroxyl oxygen. Here $\Delta\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ is about 200cm^{-1} which indicates the monodentate nature of the carboxylate group.

The amide carbonyl stretching frequency at 1620cm^{-1} is shifted to a lower frequency, $1590\text{--}1580 \text{cm}^{-1}$, on complex formation. This shows the participation of the amide carbonyl group in complex formation. Medium intensity bands observed around $490\text{--}430 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $600\text{--}515 \text{cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively.

The neutral nature of the nitrate complexes indicates the presence of two nitrate ions inside the coordination sphere. The infrared spectrum of the nitrate complex of Th^{IV} with PBCPH₂ as primary ligand shows three additional bands at 1430, 1300 and 1020 cm⁻¹ which are not present in the spectrum of PBCPH₂. These three bands are attributed respectively to ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_2 modes of the coordinated nitrate ions^{12,13}. Since the difference between ν_4 and ν_1 ($\Delta\nu = \nu_4 - \nu_1$) is ~ 130 cm⁻¹, it is inferred that the nitrate ions are coordinated unidentately to Th^{IV}. The infrared spectrum of the thiocyanato complex of Th^{IV} with PBCPH₂ as primary ligand shows some additional bands at 2050–2040, 860 and 460 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} modes of the coordinated thiocyanate ion. It has been well established that ν_{CN} occurs at a lower wave number around 2050 cm⁻¹ in N-bonded complexes as compared to the position in the case of S-bonded complexes¹⁴ appearing around 2100 cm⁻¹. Moreover, ν_{CS} mode appears in the range 720–690 cm⁻¹ for S-bonded complexes. N-bonded complexes also exhibit a single sharp band corresponding to δ_{NCS} mode¹⁵ around 480 cm⁻¹ and S-bonded complexes show several bands with lower intensities around 420 cm⁻¹. In view of these, it may be concluded that thiocyanate is coordinated unidentately to Th^{IV} through the N-atom. Coordination of thiocyanate ions is supported by the nonelectrolytic nature of the complex. In the infrared spectrum of the perchlorato complexes, there are five additional bands which have no corresponding bands in the spectrum of the ligand at 1100, 1080, 1020, 970 and 620 cm⁻¹. The three bands at 1100, 1080 and 620 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_3 modes of the coordinated perchlorate ion. This shows the unidentate coordination of ClO₄⁻ ion to Th^{IV} ion¹⁶. Two bands observed at 1020 and 970 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ν_{ClO_4} (ionic) present in the complexes. Thus, the IR spectral data of the ligand and perchlorato complexes suggest the presence of both ionic as well as monodentate coordinated perchlorate ions in these complexes. This has been supported by the conductance data which show 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour.

Thermal studies were conducted on [Th(PBCP)(NO₃)₂] and [Th(PBCP)(NCS)₂]. Independent pyrolysis experiment in air was also carried out for both the complexes studied. For this a known amount of the complex was heated in a porcelain crucible upto 750°C for about one hour. From the mass of the residue, the loss of mass was calculated in each case, which was compared with the percentage loss of mass obtained from the experiment. For the

complex, [Th(PBCP)(NO₃)₂] the TG plateau upto 227°C shows its stability and the complex decomposes after this temperature. There are two stages of decomposition as indicated by the DTG peaks observed at 242°C and 481°C. The TG curve shows a second plateau after 524°C. This shows the completion of decomposition. The decomposition at 242°C is due to the dissociation of the organic moiety which makes a mass loss of 43%. The decomposition continues with a gradual decrease in mass and a constant weight is obtained at 524°C. The residual mass obtained is about 42% which confirms that the decomposition product is ThO₂.

For the complex [Th(PBCP)(NCS)₂], the TG plateau is upto 212°C. This shows that the complex is stable upto 212°C. The DTG curve has two peaks at 231°C and 474°C indicating that the complex decomposes in two stages. The TG curve shows a second plateau after 510°C indicating the completion of decomposition. The complex shows a weight loss of 44% at 212°C due to the breaking up of the organic moiety of the complex. The decomposition continues with a gradual decrease in mass and a constant weight due to the formation of ThO₂ is obtained at 510°C. The residual weight is about 38% which corresponds to the decomposition product ThO₂. The independent pyrolysis experiment also confirms that ThO₂ is the decomposition product.

The X-ray powder patterns were recorded for the complexes [Th(PBCP)(NO₃)₂] and [Th(PBCP)(NCS)₂]. The diffraction pattern were indexed by the method developed by Hesse¹⁷ and Lipson¹⁸. Both the complexes were found to be orthorhombic. The cell parameters have been calculated using the equation, $\sin^2\theta(hkl) = Ah^2 + Bk^2 + Cl^2$, where $A = \lambda^2/4a^2$, $B = \lambda^2/4b^2$, and $C = \lambda^2/4c^2$. For [Th(PBCP)(NO₃)₂] the lattice constants are $A = 0.0028498$, $B = 0.005792$ and $C = 0.015356$ with the edge lengths $a = 14.432$ Å, $b = 10.208$ Å and $c = 6.2242$ Å. The cell volume is 916.96 (Å)³ and density is 0.7921. These gave $n = 1.164$. Thus, the number of molecules per unit cell is one. For the complex, [Th(PBCP)(NCS)₂] the lattice constants are $A = 0.00232$, $B = 0.006282$ and $C = 0.0102$ with edge lengths $a = 15.6292$, $b = 9.6948$ and $c = 7.5684$. The cell volume is 1146.7788 (Å)³ and density is 0.6588. This gave $n = 1.226$. Thus, the number of molecules per unit cell is one.

From the above studies it is concluded that the complexes have the general structure, [Th(PBCP)X₂], where X = NO₃⁻, SCN⁻ or ClO₄⁻.

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